

Survey electronic laboratory note books

Dear participants,

As part of the future introduction of electronic laboratory notebooks at institutions of the [Berlin University Alliance](#), we kindly ask you to participate in a short anonymous survey on this topic. The responsible body and head is the Computer and Medien Service of Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin (BUA project, 'Collaboratively Advancing Research Data Support', Unter den Linden 6, 10099 Berlin; Contact person: Sven Paßmann, Phone: +49 (0)30 2093 70113, E-Mail: sven.passmann@hu-berlin.de).

The aim of this survey is to determine what basic functions you need in an electronic laboratory notebook (ELN) in your field of work/discipline.

It should only take a maximum of 10 minutes to complete the survey. We will not be able to identify you from your answers. Your data will be processed confidentially and only for the scientific purpose stated. They will be stored and processed anonymously on the servers of the Humboldt University of Berlin. All survey data will be evaluated in an anonymised and aggregated form, so that no conclusions can be drawn about individual persons.

Your participation is voluntary. You can revoke your consent at any time by cancelling the survey. Your data will then not be used further. After completing the participation and sending the survey responses, it is no longer possible to revoke this consent, as your responses can no longer be assigned to you.

Please answer the following questions. Multiple selections are possible (see corresponding notes). Please also use the free text field 'Other' to add aspects that are relevant to you but have not been considered in the given questions. **Please do not enter any information in the free text fields that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.**

Thank you very much in advance for your time and your participation.

Kind regards

Dr Sven Paßmann (on behalf of the BUA CARDS project)

There are 40 questions in this survey.

Usage-friendliness

In the following section, we would like to know which aspects of user-friendliness are important to you in an electronic laboratory notebook.

If you were to work with an ELN, would a customisable user interface be important to you?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- yes
- no
- do not know

Which languages should be available? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

German

English

Other:

Which operating system should be supported? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

Linux

Windows

MacOS

Other:

How should the data be entered? (several answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- as a free text
- as a table
- as a drawing or sketch
- via chemical editor
- via scientific calculator
- via barcode scanner
- via internal links
- via external links
- via calendar
- using interfaces to other systems
- none of these

Other:

Which data formats should be supported during import? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- text
- table
- figures
- MSOffice formats
- structured formats (e.g. csv, tsv etc)
- scientific formats (e.g. e-10)
- compressed formats (e.g. zip)
- video
- audio
- none of these

Other:

Which import methods should be supported? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

drag&drop

file browsing in local storage

e-mail

Other:

Which offline functions should be supported? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- offline cache
- offline data capture
- none of these

Other:

Which data formats should be supported for export? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

formats suitable für long term archiving (e.g. txt, csv, json, etc)

formats suitable for publication (e.g. docx, odt, pdf, etc)

maschine-readable formats (e.g. json, etc)

Other:

What would you like to see in the generation and use of templates? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- creating own templates
- import own templates
- import from internet sources
- subject-specific templates
- microtiter plate templates
- none

Other:

Management

In this section, we ask you about various aspects of project management (data access assignment, laboratory organisation, standardised procedures, etc.) of an ELN.

How should collaboration be organised when sharing the ELN? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

via rights management

via role management

via comment function

none

Other:

Should standardised procedures be able to be stored in the ELN?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

yes

no

do not know

How should workflows be organised? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

via cross-project workflows

via project-related workflows

graphical workflows

Other:

Which management tools should be available? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

project management

task management

calendar

task board

milestones

none of these

Other:

Which laboratory management functions should be available? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- sample tracking
- device inventory
- device management
- freezer management
- order functions
- materials database
- none of these

Other:

Should it be possible to connect external devices (measuring devices, printers, etc.)?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- yes
- no
- do not know

Which automations should be available? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Automatic data transfer from external device
- Automated control of devices
- Data Analysis
- Automation: on request
- None of these

Other:

Which programming application interfaces should be available? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

REST API

Java API

other API

Python

command line

none of these

Other:

Data safety

The following section deals with aspects of data security and which ones you think need to be implemented in an electronic lab notebook.

How should access to the data be organised? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- via internet browser
- via desktop client
- via mobile applications
- none of these

Other:

Where should the data be stored? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- local storage
- USB-drive
- own NAS device
- storage service of the university
- cloud service of the university
- repository of the university

Other:

What security measures for user accounts in an ELN would you find helpful? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

Password

Multifactor Authentication

None of these

Other:

Research data management

In the following, we would like to know which aspects of research data management should be integrated into an electronic laboratory notebook.

Should it be possible to use discipline-specific, controlled vocabulary?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

yes

no

do not know

Should it be possible to use ontologies?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- yes
- no
- do not know

Which metadata for **identification/standards** should be able to be collected? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- access rights to the data
- licences for publications
- persistent identifier of the research facility
- persistent identifier of the scientists (e.g. ORCID)
- persistent identifier of the publication (e.g. DOI)
- persistent identifier of the repository
- name of the funding organisation
- persistent identifier of the funding organisation
- project number
- used metadata scheme
- language (e.g. used in the publication)
- version (e.g. of the publication)
- rights (e.g. of third parties)
- description (e.g. of the projects)
- geological coordinates
- none of these

Other:

Which metadata should be collected for **data collection**? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- date
- time
- data type
- data format
- data size
- location
- discipline-specific metadata
- scientist
- device
- none

Other:

Which metadata should be collected for **publication**? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- title publication
- author publication
- title journal
- year of publication
- publication volume
- name research facility
- name research institute
- none of these

Other:

How should the anti-counterfeiting protection be regulated? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- via versioning
- via time stamping
- via protocols
- via electronic signature
- via functions for accreditation
- none of these

Other:

Should exporting data from the ELN be possible according to FAIR principles?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- yes
- no
- do not know

Integration of / extensions with tools

In the following, we would like to know which additional tools you would like to see integrated into an electronic lab notebook and which extension options for external programs you would find helpful.

Which online services should be integrated in an ELN? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

JupyterHub

Gitlab/hub

none of these

Other:

Should access to various external **graphics programs be possible in an ELN? (multiple answers possible)**

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- yes
- no
- do not know

Should it be possible to access different **journals/reference tools in an ELN? (multiple answers possible)**

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- yes
- no
- do not know

Further aspects

The following aspects are not relevant for all laboratories. For this reason, the questions do not necessarily have to be answered and can simply be skipped.

If you work in a chemical laboratory: which tools should an ELN support? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

do not work in a chemical laboratory

ChemDraw

Marvin JS ChemAxon

MarvinSKetch ChemAxon

ChemDoodle

Ketcher Editor

rdkit

PubChem

OpenBabel

SciFinder

none of these

Other:

What other tools would you find useful in an ELN? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Atlas Chromatography
- PlasMapper
- SnapGene
- DNA Analysis Tool
- NWA Quality Analyst
- Vernier
- Tools to create your own plugins
- none of these

Other:

General Aspects

Concluding, there are some general aspects concerning you and the research group to which you belong.

In which research discipline is your working group embedded?

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

Please write your answer here:

What is your position in the group?

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Choose one of the following answers

If you choose 'Other:' please also specify your choice in the accompanying text field.

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Professor
- PostDoc
- Postgraduate (PhD student)
- Undergraduate (Master/Bachelor student)
- laboratory technician
- Data manager
- student assistant
- Other

How many years of experience do you have with management systems (data and/or information management)?

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- no experience
- < 1 year
- 1-2 years
- 2-4 years
- 4-8 years
- 8-12 years
- > 12 years

How long have you been using laboratory notebooks for documentation?

*

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 0 year
- < 1 year
- 1-2 years
- 2-4 years
- 4-8 years
- 8-12 years
- > 12 years

What types of data do you generate? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- experimental data
- socio-demographic data
- imaging data (MRT, M/EEG)
- climate / weather data
- survey data
- behavioral data
- geological data
- chromatographic data
- simulation data
- gene expression data
- microscopic figures

Other:

What data formats do you use? (multiple answers possible)

Please do not enter any information in the free text field that could be used to identify you or other persons or that could allow conclusions to be drawn about you or other persons.

*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- MSOffice formats (docx, xlsx, ...)
- odt (Open Document, e.g. Libre Office)
- txt
- csv
- tsv
- json
- Rdata
- SPSS formats
- XML
- Other:

Which of the following aspects are available to the working group? (multiple answers possible)

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*

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- local storage
- USB drives
- own NAS devices
- storage service at the university
- cloud service at the university
- external cloud service
- repository at the university
- external repository
- service of NFDI

Other:

Who is responsible for the following tasks? (multiple answers possible)

*

	student assistants	laboratory data technicians	data manager	PhD students	PostDocs	do not know
data collection	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
data entry	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
data cleaning	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
quality assessment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
data processing	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
data analysis	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Thank you for your participation!

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.